

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Study: Creative Pathway in the Development of Scientific Literacy in Higher Education

Section	Item	Description	Location in Manuscript
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review	Title page
Abstract	2	Provide a structured summary	Abstract
Introduction	3	Describe the rationale	Introduction
Objectives	4	Provide explicit objectives or questions	Introduction – Research Questions
Methods	5	Eligibility criteria	Methods – Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria
Methods	6	Information sources	Methods – Literature Search Strategy
Methods	7	Search strategy	Methods – Keyword Formula
Methods	8	Selection process	Methods – PRISMA Screening
Methods	9	Data collection process	Methods – Data Collection
Methods	10	Data items	Methods – Data Extraction
Methods	11	Study risk of bias	Not applicable (bibliometric review)
Results	16	Study selection	Results – PRISMA Flow Diagram
Results	17	Study characteristics	Results – Descriptive Analysis
Discussion	23	Discussion of results	Discussion section
Other	27	Availability of data and materials	Data Availability section